

Monitoring of Helheim Glacier Dynamics Using the Open-Source High-Resolution Satellite Imagery

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Abstract: In recent years, climate change-driven pressures have been causing accelerated ice loss on the Greenland Ice Sheet, leading to the gradual sea level rise. Monitoring of spatio-temporal changes (STCs) created by ice melt and calving is essential for comprehending present glacial dynamics, as well as for the forecasting of future trends. In this study, we investigate the suitability of open-source high-resolution (HR) satellite imagery from various satellite constellations for monitoring and quantifying of multi-year glacial dynamics. Monitoring of glacial dynamics was applied for a multi-year period (2010–2023) over the Helheim Glacier, one of the largest outlet glaciers of the Greenland Ice Sheet. Multi-year STCs at the Helheim Glacier were determined using the open-source satellite imagery provided by Google Earth Engine (2010–2016) and the Planet constellation (2016–2023). To determine multi-year glacier dynamics, the terminus of the Helheim Glacier was extracted from available satellite imagery. Intensity of linear and areal STCs was calculated for each extracted glacier terminus using the Digital shoreline analysis system (DSAS) extension for ArcGIS 10.1. Available HR open-source satellite imagery has provided insights into the multi-year glacial dynamics of the Helheim Glacier. Although determined multi-year glacier dynamics are highly variable, prominent trend of accelerated retreat at Helheim Glacier was observed for analysed timeframe.

Keywords: glacial dynamics; Helheim; remote sensing; climate change; PlanetScope.

1 Introduction

The Greenland Ice Sheet is experiencing accelerated ice melting and calving due to intensified climate change and gradual sea level rise (Jiang et al. 2020, Box et al. 2022). Monitoring of spatio-temporal changes (STCs) related to the ice melt and calving is crucial for understanding present glacial dynamics and forecasting future trends (Evans et al. 2022). Satellite imagery is emerging as practical and accurate method for monitoring glacial dynamics over large and remote areas (Otosaka et al. 2023). Despite the widespread utilization of open-source imagery with medium spatial resolution (e.g. Landsat or Sentinel), application of high-resolution (HR) satellite imagery remains limited (MacGregor et al. 2020). Therefore, in this study we investigate the suitability of open-source HR satellite imagery from various satellite constellations for monitoring and quantifying of multi-year glacial dynamics.

2 Materials and methods

Monitoring of glacial dynamics was applied for a multi-year period (2010–2023) over the Helheim Glacier (Figure 1B), one of the largest outlet glaciers of the Greenland Ice Sheet (Figure 1A). Several earlier studies have reported intensive retreat of Helheim Glacier (Holland et al. 2016, Stevens et al. 2022).

Figure 1. Study area covering Helheim Glacier (Greenland).

Open-source satellite imagery was obtained from two sources, Google Earth Engine (2010–2016) and PlanetScope (2016–2023) (Figure 2).

Satellite imagery covering the Helheim Glacier, acquired through Google Earth Engine, represents HR imagery collected by commercial satellites on various dates, spanning from May 2010 to August 2016. These RGB satellite images were georeferenced (Affine transformation), utilizing multiple tie points situated on hard rock surfaces located outside the dynamic areas of the glacier. Since 2016, multispectral HR imagery collected by the PlanetScope constellation has been available for the Helheim Glacier, with data available for nearly every day.

Figure 2. Open-source high-resolution satellite imagery used for analysis of multi-year glacier dynamics (2010–2023).

Thus, HR PlanetScope images with no cloud cover were acquired for each year in the period between 2016 and 2023.

The glacier terminus was manually vectorized at a scale of 1:3000 from each acquired HR satellite image, spanning from 2010. to 2023. To aid manual vectorization, the Normalized Difference Glacier Index (NDGI) was calculated based on each multispectral PlanetScope image using the following equation (1).

$$NDGI = \frac{B_{Green} - B_{NIR}}{B_{Green} + B_{NIR}} \quad (1)$$

The displacement of the glacier terminus, i.e., glacier advance or retreat, was analyzed using the Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) extension for ArcGIS 10.1. DSAS allows comparison of line features and calculation of several metrics related to linear STCs (Peppia et al. 2020). Spacing length of transects within DSAS was set to 50 meters, thus enabling the measurement of linear displacement at each 50-meter interval along the entire length of the terminus. In total around 110 transects were used to calculate linear STCs within each mapped terminus. Along with linear STCs, detection of multi-year areal STCs was also performed.

3 Results

The intensity of the detected multi-year linear movement of the glacier terminus is characterized by very high interannual variability and interchange of retreat and advancement phases (Figure 3, Figure 4).

Several phases of intensive glacier retreat can be identified from the detected linear STCs, with average linear retreat ranging from 0.85 km (2010–2012) up to 1.95 km (2019–2020). Maximum retreat of glacier terminus was detected in period between 2018 and 2019, with linear retreat of over 3.5 km. Intensive glacier retreat was in general followed by advancement of terminus in next analyzed period (e.g. 2012–2014, 2017–2018, 2019–2020, 2020–2021, 2022–2023). However, in general the intensity of this advancement was lower than the preceding retreat, ranging from 0.21 km up to 0.82 km. The only exception is the last analyzed period (2022–2023), when a very strong progression was detected, with an average linear

Figure 3. Comparison between intensity of average linear multi-year STCs and occurrence of prolonged heatwaves.

advancement of 2.68 km. Occurrence of such rapid advancement could potentially lead to the very intensive calving and glacier retreat in the following few years.

It should be noted that glacier retreat is more dominant, as within the whole studied period (2010–2023) glacier terminus has retreated for 1.22 km.

Figure 4. Detected multi-year linear movement of the glacier terminus.

Detected multi-year areal STCs further corroborate the gradual predominant retreat of Helheim Glacier (Figure 5). In overall, Helheim Glacier has retreated for about 6.25 km² within the studied period, thus confirming the predominant ice melt and ice loss. Besides detection of multi-temporal areal STCs, analyzed satellite imagery has allowed detection of large icebergs, formed by gradual calving from glacier terminus (Figure 5).

4 Discussion

Open-source satellite imagery proved to be a good basis for detailed detection of complex glacial dynamics, both in terms of linear and areal STCs. Multispectral HR imagery from PlanetScope constellation has especially great potential for monitoring of glacial dynamics, as it features (1) spectral bands required for easier detection of ice, (2) high spatial resolution required for detection of STCs and (3) daily temporal resolution. The daily temporal resolution

enables the detection of multi-year STCs within such remote areas with frequent cloud and snow cover.

Figure 5. Aerial STCs detected at Helheim Glacier within the whole analyzed time-frame (2010–2023).

Multi-year glacial dynamics detected from open-source satellite imagery corresponds to the results of earlier research (Holland et al. 2016, Stevens et al. 2022). The detected variability in multi-year glacial dynamics can be attributed to the occurrence of prolonged heatwaves, which have been identified as the main cause of ice cover reduction (Neff et al. 2014, Bonne et al. 2015, Tedesco and Fettweis 2020, Jiang et al. 2020). Furthermore, previous research has shown that beside multi-year variability, glacial dynamics at Helheim glacier are also characterized by intensive seasonal variability (Kehrl et al. 2017). Therefore, in future research, we plan to investigate the link between heatwaves and seasonal glacial dynamics in more detail.

5 Conclusions

Carried research has demonstrated that open-source HR satellite imagery has great potential for monitoring of complex glacial dynamics over large and remote areas. Due to the combination of high spectral, temporal and spatial resolution, imagery from PlanetScope constellation has proven particularly effective for detection and quantification of glacial dynamics. Therefore, such open-source HR satellite imagery could be used for monitoring of multi-year and seasonal glacial dynamics over other glaciers of the Greenland Ice Sheet and other parts of the World.

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6 References

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